

Gender differences in the use of ICT for health purposes and vaccine acceptance among Estonian older adults during COVID-19 pandemic

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Keywords

Older adults, ICT use, online health information behavior, Covid-19 vaccination

EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Topic

The purpose of this article is to present the results of a survey on the use of information and communication technology (ICT) for health purposes and vaccine acceptance conducted among 50+ Estonians during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Value of the contribution

The COVID-19 crisis has brought senior citizens into the social spotlight as the most vulnerable population to diseases. This study contributes to the gender dimensions of health information research among older adults in Covid-19 lockdown. ICT adoption among older adults has risen steadily in affluent societies over the last decade (Rinderud, 2021; Anderson & Perrin, 2017). However, in poorer countries seniors are often referred to as being deprived of the benefits of digital society (König et al, 2018). Statistics reveal a large digital divide between generations especially in Eastern European countries, and within the elderly population itself (People in the EU, 2017). 98% of EU-28 citizens aged 16 to 24 years used the internet within the last 12 months, but only 78% of those aged 55 to 64 years and 48% of those aged 65 to 74 years used the internet within the last 12 months (Eurostat, 2021). Statistics also suggests that 17% of the 55-64-year-olds and 44% of the 65-74-year-olds living in Estonia have never used the internet (European, 2019). Among 75-year-olds, the corresponding figure is 68% (ibid.)

Earlier studies have revealed that older people are not particularly interested in seeking for health information in online environment (Menendez Alvarez-Dardet et al, 2020; Niemelä, Huotari, and Kortelainen, 2012). By contrast, this study revealed that 50+ people in Estonia are enthusiastic ICT users and health information seekers. Especially, well-educated men were most keen on health apps and getting vaccinated against the virus.

Research outline

Problem. If we were to find anything positive in the COVID-19 pandemic, then it most certainly has drawn attention to older members of society as well as their use of ICT (Callow et al, 2021). ICT provides a good opportunity for older people to cope independently during the crises (Arthanat, 2021; Nimrod, 2021), however, studies refer that many older people have problems in using computers and smart devices (Jokisch et al, 2020; Choi, 2019; Enwald et al, 2018). It has been established that younger people, women and those with the highest education are more interested in online health information seeking and they also exhibit better health behavior at least in some respects (Chaudhuri et al., 2013; Ek, 2015; Enwald et al., 2017).

This paper sets out to study the use of ICT for health purposes among older adults (50+) living in a small eastern European country Estonia. As the use of the internet decreases among people in Estonia already in their 50s, this study centres on adults aged 50 and older. 75+ were included because official statistics do not cover them in terms of internet. Older adults' willingness to contact health professionals online as well as use of various digital health applications; and finally, their acceptance of COVID-19 vaccines was also analyzed. Estonia is often referred for its digital success, e.g., for its solutions like digital signatures, electronic tax claims, e-Business Register, and Industry 4.0 (e-Estonia). However, it is also marked as a country with a high poverty rate among older people and digital divide between generations (European, 2019). It is paramount to study older adults' online health information behavior in a country where the use of technology could enable to reduce social inequalities within the disadvantaged population groups and facilitate independent aging. No special studies on online health information seeking among older people have been conducted in Estonia before.

Methodology. A survey of 501 older adults living in Estonia was conducted in the summer of 2020. The market research company Norstat questioned half of the participants by telephone and another half over the phone between 20 July and 3 August.

The whole questionnaire included 15 substantive multiple-choice questions as well as questions regarding the socio-demographic profile of the respondents (gender, age, nationality, education level, employed/unemployed) and monthly income. In this paper the following questions were included: First, it was asked – do you have access to a personal computer or similar digital device which can be used for conducting online searches? A 2-point scale was used 'yes, I do/ no, I don't. Second, the author was interested when did they last conduct an online search on health, illnesses, or disease prevention? The answers included: in the past 7 days/ in the past 30 days/ in the past 6 months or less often/ I don't look for information about health or illnesses on the Web. Third, it was asked – during the COVID-19 lockdown, how important was it for you to have access to a doctor from a distance (e.g. exchanging e-mails, texting, video consultations)? The respondent

had to choose between important/ not very important/ rather unimportant. Fourth question was – would you have any use for digital health solutions or services? For instance, the kind that allow you to consult with medical personnel, monitor your blood pressure or sleep patterns, check your heart rate, remind you to take a pill or keep you company? (Yes/ No/ I don't know.) Fifth, the author wanted to know if they would like to get vaccinated if the opportunity arose. The answers included options of course/ I doubt it/ no. Socioeconomic indicators included gender, age, nationality, education level, employment, and monthly income.

The sample included 204 men and 297 women from age 50 onwards. The oldest participant was 94, the youngest ones 50 years old. The median age was 65. The sample was representative in terms of gender, age, and nationality.

Findings. The survey results indicated that 79% (i.e. 4 out of 5) of the respondents had access to a computer or a smart device. Male (86%) reported better access than women (74%). Interestingly enough, the age group 75+ did not actually lag far behind. Although 50+ female internet users in general search for more health information, more men than women aged 65+ with higher education had gone online to search for health information in the past 30 days (63% and 54% respectively). Women (44%) felt more important to have access to a doctor from a distance during the COVID-19 lockdown (exchanging e-mails, texting, video consultations) than their male counterparts (30%). However, men, especially those with higher qualifications, expressed much more interest in various digital health gadgets and services, e.g., electronic sleep trackers and aids, blood pressure and pulse monitors, and robot communication. Men were also more willing to get vaccinated against Covid-19. This trend was evident in all age groups, but especially among the retirees. Males with higher education working in senior positions stood out from the rest in this respect. Thus, it was not confirmed that men in general appear to be more indifferent to their health and disease prevention.

Conclusions: Despite the digital divide between generations in Estonia there is a clear interest among many older adults to use ICT. Men's affection to digital health devices gives us reason to hope that digital information sources have every potential of improving their overall health behavior in the future. Nevertheless, the digital skills of the less educated and the unemployed, both men and women alike, call for further enhancement.

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